

Effective AI Model Monitoring in the Financial Industry Using Hypothesis Testing and Control Charts

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Abstract

Model monitoring has become a critical risk management activity as Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications expand to many aspects of our daily lives and governments take notice. Whether a model is performing as intended often involves several metrics that monitor different interests including the model's statistical performance and the intended business outcome. Traditionally, the data scientists have recommended the use of a model based on its statistical performance. We argue that this approach has limitations as it does not account for the business key performance indicators (KPI¹) that the business leaders rely on to evaluate the model effectiveness. In this paper, we propose a methodology to link these two evaluation methods such that deterioration or improvement in the business KPI can be traced back to the model. In addition, we propose that the use of hypothesis testing and/or control charts can further enhance the evaluation of the model performance during the monitoring period.

Key Words: artificial intelligence, machine learning, multivariate statistical process control, model monitoring, monitoring thresholds, false discovery rate, hypothesis testing, control charts.

1. Introduction

Organizations have been using quantitative models to inform or support decisions for decades. For example, financial analysts have long used the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) to help relate the required return on an investment to the risk of that investment since the model was developed in the early 1960s [1]. The release of the FICO score in 1990s has helped generalize the use of quantitative models in consumers' credit risk assessment [2]. In these cases, and many others, the appeal of the quantitative models lies on the promise that they can provide a data-driven, rational, and consistent approach to business decision-making. Given the recent emergence and popularity of artificial intelligence (AI) systems, and their ability to use more powerful algorithms to process large quantity of data, the reliance on quantitative methods to inform or support decisions will only increase across organizations. Assessing the effectiveness of these quantitative methods have traditionally focused on their initial review. In this paper, we propose that an effective performance monitoring is a critical model risk management practice and should play an equally important role in deciding the continued use of the quantitative models deployed in production.

1.1 Managing Model Risk

In April 2011, the Federal Reserve (Fed) and the Office of the Currency (OCC) of the United States released their joint supervisory guidance on model risk management (a.k.a. SR 11-7) [3]. Initially directed to banking organizations, this guidance acknowledges the role that quantitative models played in the risky decisions that led to the US Financial Crisis of 2008 which also adversely impacted many economies around the world [4]. This guidance recommends that banking organizations be attentive to the potentially adverse consequences of decisions based on incorrect

¹ In general, KPI are defined as quantifiable measures of performance over time for a specific business objective.

or misused models and address them through active model risk management. Indeed, even well conceived, and constructed models do produce erroneous output and the size of the error tends to increase with time [5]; which underscores the importance of monitoring a model from its inception through its retirement. The objectives of model monitoring can be several folds and include whether a model is implemented, used, or performing as intended. In this paper, we focus on the monitoring of the model performance as it is critical in deciding whether a model should be implemented or should continue to be used.

1.2 Formalizing Model Monitoring

SR 11-7 defines a model as a quantitative method, system or approach that applies statistical, economic, financial, or mathematical theories, techniques, and assumptions to process input data into quantitative estimates. In this paper, we adopt this definition although it may not cover some engineered or machine-based systems that process inputs into outputs such as predictions, recommendations, or decisions in automated or semi-automated manner for pre-specified objectives². Regardless of the definition adopted, the monitoring of a model remains an important risk management practice that evaluates the continued model effectiveness considering the constant change in the model's business and socio-economic environment.

Mathematically, model monitoring can be formulated as follows:

Let Y , a target variable that we would like to link to a set of input variables X :

$$X \rightarrow Y$$

Let n be the number of observations available for this modeling exercise:

$$[Y_t] \text{ and } [X_t] \text{ for } t = 1, 2, 3 \dots n \text{ observations; } t \text{ is an index}$$

We estimate a link function f on a subset of the n observations:

$$\text{Trained Model: } \hat{Y}_t = f(X_t); t = 1, 2, 3 \dots k; k < n \quad (1)$$

We first evaluate the fit of this trained model through an error metric:

$$e_{train} = M(Y_t - \hat{Y}_t) \text{ for } t = 1, 2, 3 \dots k \quad (2)$$

Then we test the trained model on the remaining subset unseen by the model:

$$e_{test} = M(Y_t - \hat{Y}_t) \text{ for } t = k + 1, k + 2, k + 3 \dots n \quad (3)$$

where $M(\cdot)$ is an evaluation function, the smaller the better

In general, the model performance is considered to be acceptable when the model error is low and is stable between the training and test data i.e:

$$e_{test} \approx e_{train} \quad (4)$$

After the model is deployed in production, its performance is evaluated on monitoring data:

$$e_{mtr} = M(Y_t - \hat{Y}_t) \text{ for } t = n + 1, n + 2, n + 3 \dots m \quad (5)$$

The main question that the monitoring is concerned with is not only whether the the model performance has degraded but how significant has been the degradation:

$$\text{for } t > n; \text{ is } M(e_{test}) \leq M(e_{mtr}) < M(e_{test}) + a \quad (5);$$

where "a" measures the extent of the model degradation compared to the testing data.

² National Institute of Standards and Technologies' definition of AI system is broader than that of SR 11-7 [6].

2. Literature Review

Search in google reveals that model monitoring is not sufficiently studied in academic circles. Most of the existing guidance are provided by regulators (Fed, OCC and others through SR 11-7), industry consultants such as Medium [7] or vendors such as Amazon Web Services [8]. Monitoring the performance of a model involves the periodic measurement of its performance to detect signs of moderate or large shifts and to investigate the underlying cause. In business setting, this measurement has often been conducted by two main stakeholders. On one hand, the data scientists who developed the model, tend to rely on statistical measures. On the other hand, the business leaders measure this performance through business KPI.

2.1 Statistical Performance Metrics

The statistical metrics required to evaluate a model performance often depend on the model types. In general, models can be grouped into two broad categories namely classification and regression models. In this paper, we will focus on classification models.

Classification models are used to predict outcomes that are categorical in nature. An example of classification model is one that predicts whether a customer applying for a financial product (credit card, deposit, or loan account etc.) should be approved or rejected. For such models, the literature recommends several statistical performance metrics to evaluate how well the model can distinguish between the possible categories (approved or rejected, in this case).

For a binary classifier (i.e two possible categories), the following metrics are often recommended:

$$\text{True Positive Rate (TPR) a.k.a. Recall or Sensitivity} = \frac{t_p}{t_p + f_n} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Positive Predictive Value (PPV) a.k.a. Precision} = \frac{t_p}{t_p + f_p} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Accuracy (ACC)} = \frac{t_p + t_n}{t_p + f_p + t_n + f_n} \quad (8)$$

where t_p , f_p , t_n , and f_n are the numbers of true positives, false positives, true negatives, and false negatives, respectively, and

$$F_1 = 2 * \frac{FPR * TPR}{FPR + TPR} \quad (9)$$

Additional metrics include:

- the area under the receiver operating curve (AUROC)
- the area under the precision-recall curve (AUPRC).

2.2 Business Key Performance Indicators

The data scientist(s) who developed a model are in most cases not its primary users. Like a software developer whose product is often consumed by staff with varying knowledge of coding, the data scientists develop a model to help meet a broader business objective. In fact, in many business organizations, the model output is just one out of several pieces of information that contribute to the final outcome, be it prediction, recommendation, or decision.

Figure 1: Models in business decision-making

As such, the indicators of success that appeal to the business leaders can be very different from the statistical performance metrics that the data scientists care about.

Examples of KPIs	
Business Objective	Business KPI
Reduce credit card fraud risk	Credit card fraud loss
Improve customer satisfaction	Net promoter Score
Increase staff retention	Employee Survey Score

Table 1: Examples of KPI Setting

Table 1 shows examples of KPI corresponding to some business objectives. For example, to meet the business objective of reducing credit card fraud risk, the business leaders may track credit card loss amount whereas the data scientists would be more interested in their model's discriminatory power i.e the model's ability to distinguish a valid transaction from a fraudulent one.

3. Our Proposal

3.1 The problem

The use of different performance metrics by the data scientists and the business leaders is a problem that can have serious consequences for the business when these performance metrics indicate opposing conclusions. From the data scientists who may spend significant amount of time and resources in roots cause analysis to the business leaders who may embark in uninformed post-model adjustments, lack of trust in the model output can become the central issue and one of the following errors may ensue.

Type 1 error or false positive:

If $KPI_{mnr} \neq KPI_{t0}$ then re – develop the model although $M(e_{mnr}) \leq M(e_{test})$

Type II error or false negative:

If $KPI_{mnr} \approx KPI_{t0}$ then continue model use although $M(e_{mnr}) > M(e_{test})$

3.2 Reframing the Problem

We found that at the heart of the problem caused by the diverging performance assessment between the data scientists and the business leaders is the inability to measure the contribution of the model to the final business outcome. To solve this problem, we propose to **link the statistical performance to the business KPI**.

In mathematical terms, this proposal can be written as follows:
Estimate "a" as: $a = f(b)$ such that:

$$M(e_{mnr}) \leq M(e_{test}) + a \equiv KPI_{t0} - \mathbf{b} \leq KPI_{mnr} \leq KPI_{t0} + \mathbf{b}$$

Where:

\mathbf{a} is the tolerable deviation from e_{test} measured on the test data.

\mathbf{b} is the tolerable deviation from the KPI_{t0} value set by the business owner.

4. An Illustrative Example

4.1 Model Description

Credit card fraud is a serious problem for banks and other lenders. A 2021's report by the Federal Trade Commission found credit card fraud to be the second most reported identity theft type in the U.S behind government documents and benefits fraud [9]. Nilson, a leading publication covering payment systems estimated the losses associated with credit card fraud to be \$32 billion worldwide, \$12 billion of which were incurred in the US in 2021 [10]. It follows that detecting and preventing credit card fraud is a top risk management objective for card's issuers and processors as well as merchants.

In this paper, we illustrate our proposal with credit card fraud data publicly available on Kaggle.com. The anonymized dataset, released by Vesta Corporation as part of an open data science competition can be summarized as follows:

- Number of unique transactions: 590,540 including 20,663 fraud cases
- 394 variables including transaction status, transaction date, product code, transaction amount, IP address, number of days between transactions and more.
- The target variable is the transaction status, labeled as "IsFraud". It takes the value:
 - 1 if the transaction is fraudulent.
 - 0 otherwise.

After data preparation and cleaning, we split the dataset into training data (53%), out-of-sample or test data (23%) and out-of-time or monitoring data (24%).

Then, through feature engineering, we reduced the number of variables from 394 to 48.

Finally, we fit the following random forest classifier after a model selection process described in Appendix 1.

$$rf_max6 = RandomForestClassifier(max_depth = 6, random_state = 42)$$

4.2. Model Outcome Analysis

The performance of the fitted random forest algorithm can be summarized as follows:

Metric	AUPRC	F1_Score	Precision	Recall
Test Data	0.12	0.91	0.96	0.88

Table 1: Performance of rf_max6

Out of the four metrics in the table 1 above we will focus on the F1_score and the AUPRC. Indeed, due to the severance imbalance³ in the credit card fraud use case data, these two metrics are more appropriate than the others because they account for both precision and recall metrics. It's worth noting that this outcome analysis focuses solely on the model statistical performance. In general, when this performance is reasonably strong and/or better than that of the available

³ The proportion of fraud cases is 3.5% which is very small and indicative of an imbalanced dataset.

alternative, the model is approved for deployment. For an initial model review, this outcome analysis may be acceptable. But when it comes to model monitoring, which is the focus of this paper, this analysis is insufficient as it completely ignores the KPI which reflects the business leaders' gauge of the model effectiveness.

It might be tempting to assume that these two measures would converge such that when one indicates that the model performance is not acceptable, the other would indicate a similar conclusion. But that is not often the case in practice. When these two measures offer contradictory conclusions, the consequences can involve significant waste of time and resources. To solve this issue, we propose to link the statistical performance to the business KPI.

4.3. Linking the statistical performance to the business KPI

The business leaders, in their capacity of model owner in many organisations, often hold a higher authority over the data scientist as to whether the model is meeting the target business objective. Therefore, **we consider the business KPI to be a constraint**. Then, the task becomes to find a statistical metric that can concur with this business KPI such that an improvement or deterioration in the business KPI can be traced back to the model. Let's illustrate our proposal with the credit card fraud use case.

Let consider the following cost structure 1 which describes the average business cost associated with the model error as evaluated by the business leaders:

Cost structure 1: FN more important than FP

- \$0 = True negative or TN (the model accurately identifies a valid transaction)
- \$3 = False positive or FP (the model flags a valid transaction as fraudulent)
- \$0 = True Positive or TP (the model accurately flags a fraudulent transaction)
- \$60⁴ = False Negative or FN (the model flags a fraudulent transaction as valid)

We can then compute for a given data sample⁵, the statistical performance metric value, and the associated business cost in terms of loss amount from credit card fraud. The figure 1 below shows the relationship between these two performance measures.

Figure 1: Relationship between credit card fraud loss amount and AUPRC

The expectation in linking the statistical performance metric to the business KPI is to establish a monotonic relationship between these two measures. For the fraud use case under study, this

⁴ When fraud occurs, the associated cost can include the chargeback amount to the merchant and the cost to the card issuer in terms of lost transaction fee and investigating the fraud to recoup the stolen money. In the event of FP, the main cost is the loss of transaction fee, which is often significantly lower than the chargeback amount and the investigation cost. This explains the much higher weight assigned to FN than FP.

⁵ The modeling data are grouped in 36 samples, each containing 12,500 credit card transactions.

monotonic relationship would signal that an increase in the fraud loss amount would correspond to an increase in the model's AUPRC. At minimum, the Figure 1 above does not show such monotonic relationship between these two measures. At first, this result may be surprising considering that the AUPRC is the favorite metric when measuring the performance of a binary classifier on serious imbalanced data like the credit card data under consideration.

But, as we revisit the definition of the AUPRC, we realize that this metric is mainly focused on the positive class [11]. To verify our assumption let's consider the cost structure 2 defined as follows:

Cost structure 2: FP more important than FN

- \$0 = True negative or TN (the model accurately identifies a valid transaction)
- \$3 = False positive or FP (the model flags a valid transaction as fraudulent)
- \$60 = True Positive or TP (the model accurately flags a fraudulent transaction)
- \$0 = False Negative or FN (the model flags a fraudulent transaction as valid)

Figure 2: relationship between fraud loss and AUPRC when FP more important than FN

Figure 2 shows a much stronger monotonic relationship between the statistical performance metric and the business KPI as we would expect.

However, for the credit card fraud use case, the cost structure 1 makes more business sense due to higher cost associated with the FN. To proceed, we investigate a different statistical performance measure namely the F1_score that is also suitable for imbalance data.

Figure 2: Relationship between credit card fraud loss amount and F1_score

Figure 2 shows some linearity between the fraud loss amount and F1_score. This is an encouraging observation. Noting that the F1_score is a particular form of F_beta_score (F_β), we investigate other forms of F_β as follows:

$$F_\beta = (1 + \beta^2) * \frac{precision * recall}{(\beta^2 * precision) + recall}$$

From the above formula, we derive the following:

$$F_\beta \rightarrow precision \text{ if } \beta \rightarrow 0$$

$$F_\beta \rightarrow recall \text{ if } \beta \rightarrow \infty$$

In particular:

$$F_1 = (1 + 1^2) * \frac{precision * recall}{(1^2 * precision) + recall} = 2 * \frac{precision * recall}{precision + recall} = \frac{2}{\frac{1}{recall} + \frac{1}{precision}},$$

which is the harmonic mean of precision and recall,

$$F_2 = (1 + 2^2) * \frac{precision * recall}{(2^2 * precision) + recall} = 5 * \frac{precision * recall}{(4 * precision) + recall} = \frac{5}{\frac{4}{recall} + \frac{1}{precision}},$$

which is essentially a weighted harmonic mean with a higher weight toward recall, ...and so on.

When we investigate the relationship between the fraud loss amount and various forms of F_β , we obtain the figure 3 below.

Figure 3: Relationship between mean fraud loss amount and various forms of F_β

Figure 3 shows the monotonic relationship that we are seeking. For the credit card fraud use case, this relationship is linear and gets stronger from F1_score to F4_score as measured by the regression's R^2 . While we can investigate the strength of this relationship further with higher values of β until the R^2 peaks, we stop at $\beta = 3$ which already yields a strong relationship with

$R^2 = 94\%$. Note that, at two decimal points, the R^2 does not change from $\beta = 3$ to $\beta = 4$ (0.9384~0.9422~0.94). Therefore, F_3 is the statistical performance measure to link to the business KPI for monitoring purpose.

A reasonable explanation of this strong monotonic relationship is the feature of F_β that allows to vary the value of β to be directionally consistent with the higher weight (or cost) assigned to false negatives than that assigned to false positives in the specified cost structure 1.

Assuming the strong linear relationship observed between these two measures holds, we can expect the F_3 to help explain the deterioration or improvement in the business KPI.

4.4. Model Monitoring

Now that we have identified the appropriate statistical performance measure to link to the business KPI, the next step is to specify the monitoring parameters. To do so, we follow the steps below:

- Order either the F_3 or the fraud loss amount from highest to lowest.
- Identify the value of the statistical performance metric F_{β_0} corresponding to the **target loss amount KPI_{t0}** set by the business leaders at the time of model development.
- Identify the value of the statistical performance metric F_{β_1} corresponding to **KPI_{t1}** . i. e the **maximum fraud loss amounts tolerable** by the business.
- Set the initial monitoring thresholds based on F_{β_0} and F_{β_1} .
- Finally, we evaluate the monitoring data based on these thresholds.

4.5. Model Monitoring Illustration

To illustrate the proposed model monitoring, let consider the credit card fraud use case.

- We start by ordering the values of the F_3 and the corresponding fraud loss amount.

Samples	s1	s2	s3	s4	s5	S6	...	s9	S10	...	S35	s36	Mean
F3	0.8611	0.8623	0.8633	0.8634	0.8657	0.8665	...	0.8704	0.8731	...	0.9068	0.9132	0.8850
Fraud Loss	102,978	101,772	100,008	101,973	100,248	96,390	...	90,558	88,749	...	60,384	56,604	79,823

Table 2: F3 for combined training and evaluation data grouped in 36 samples.

- For $KPI_{t0} = 90,000$, we identify 0.873 in table 2 as the corresponding $F_3 = F_{\beta_0}$
- For $KPI_{t1} = 100,000$, we identify 0.867 in table 2 as the corresponding $F_3 = F_{\beta_1}$
- Then, we can now set the initial monitoring thresholds:
 - $F_3 \geq 0.873$ = green zone = performance is satisfactory.
 - $0.867 \leq F_3 < 0.873$ = yellow zone = performance is under watch.
 - $F_3 < 0.867$ = red zone = performance may not be satisfactory
- Now let's evaluate the monitoring data based on these thresholds:

Assuming the 36 samples constructed from the training and validation data (see Table 2) are representative of the credit card fraud patterns for the foreseeable future, we derive the probability of the model performance being unsatisfactory to be 17% as F3 is lower than 0.867 for only 6 out 36 samples. We test this hypothesis using the monitoring dataset. This dataset includes 140,540 transactions which we grouped in 12 samples and compute their F3 values as shown in Table 3 below; see Appendix 3 for the F3 and fraud loss amount corresponding to all the 12 samples.

Samples	s1	s2	s3	s4	s5	s6	s7	...	s10	s11	s12	s12	Mean
F3	0.8105	0.8393	0.8741	0.8764	0.8807	0.8819	0.8839	...	0.8898	0.8964	0.8965	0.8999	0.8763
Fraud Loss	129,270	109,578	81,855	80,229	76,812	77,874	77,421	...	72,135	65259	66,228	64,497	81,115

Table 3: F3 for monitoring data grouped in 12 samples.

Table 3 presents the monitoring F3 values in ascending order. Consistent with the decision rule specified in bullet point d. above, this table shows that F3 values below 0.867 correspond to fraud loss amount above the business tolerance of \$100,000. In addition, the 17% probability of the

model performance being unsatisfactory holds as only 2 out of these 12 monitoring samples have F3 values below 0.867. In other words, the model’s statistical performance concurs with its business performance.

That said, the monotonically decreasing relationship between the F3 and the fraud loss amount may not hold for all values of F3. For example, in table 3, when F3 increases from 0.8807 (s5) to 0.8819 (s6), the corresponding fraud loss amount also increases from 76,812 to 77,874 instead of decreasing. Eventually this volatility in individual F3 values can lead to a scenario whereby a value of F3 in the yellow or green zone may correspond to a fraud loss amount above the business tolerance, which, in turn, may lead to opposing conclusions about the model performance between the data scientists on one hand and the business leaders on the other hand. Therefore, it is worth supplementing the monitoring of individual F3 values with the monitoring of a more stable statistic as described in section 4.5.1 below.

4.5.1. Hypothesis Testing in model monitoring.

Hypothesis testing is a popular and well-established procedure that statisticians have used for decades to assess whether a particular viewpoint is likely to be true [12]. Considering the significant time and resources that are unnecessary wasted in model’s roots cause analysis or redevelopment, hypothesis testing can undeniably provide valuable insight in whether a model is performing as intended. In this section, we apply hypothesis testing to the mean⁶ F3 values derived from the credit card fraud data.

We first construct the sampling distribution of mean F_3 (see Figure 4) based on 10,000 bootstrap samples drawn with replacement from the 12 monitoring samples shown in table 3.

Figure 4: Sampling distribution of bootstrapped mean F3

The sampling distribution of the mean F3 reasonably approximates the normal distribution with the following parameters:

- mean = 0.8763, equal to the 0.8763 value of the monitoring sample shown in table 3
- standard deviation = 0.0079

Then, we can specify the following hypothesis test at 5% significance level to test whether the mean F3 = 0.8763 derived from of the monitoring data (see table 3) is significantly different from the hypothesized mean F3 value of 0.8850 derived from the original 36 samples:

⁶ We could have selected a different statistic such as proportion, standard deviation, or others.

$$H_0: E[F_3] = 0.8850$$

$$H_1: E[F_3] \neq 0.8850$$

Based on the sampling distribution shown in Figure 4, we can also calculate the bootstrap p-value:
 $p - value = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N s_i = 0.1112$

Where:

- $N=10,000$ bootstrap samples
- s_i represents each of these 10,000 samples with a mean $F_3 > 0.8850$.

This p-value is within the 95% confidence interval [0.025,0.975]. Therefore, we do not reject the null hypothesis. This result further supports the prior assessment in section 4.5.e. which found no statistically significant evidence of model performance deterioration based on the monitoring data.

4.5.2 Notes on control charts

Control charts have been routinely used to monitor process quality in many industries including manufacturing, healthcare, and others. In this paper, we propose that control charts can also aid in monitoring the performance of quantitative models.

For the credit card fraud use case, we can build the control chart shown in figure 5 below.

Figure 5: Control chart for the F3 values

In the above control chart, the F3 values derived from the 36 samples shown in table 2 are represented by the blue markers; they are used to set the control limits. Considering the size of each of these 36 samples is reasonably large (12,500 observations), we can set the control limits in standard deviation (sigma) increments:

- The centerline (CL) is 0.8850 = the mean of the F3 values for the 36 samples
- 1 sigma deviation from the CL (= [0.8709,0.892]) is considered a non-significant shift.
- 2 sigma deviation from the CL (= [0.8567,0.9134]) is considered a moderate shift.
- 3 sigma deviation from the CL is considered a significant shift:
 - Upper control limit (UCL) = 0.9275 = 3 sigma deviation above the CL
 - Lower control limit (LCL) = 0.8426 = 3 sigma deviation below the CL
- Any F3 value beyond the LCL or the UCL is a signal, that is, an indication that the model performance may be unsatisfactory.

Among the several insights that can be drawn from this control chart, we note that all the 36 F_3 values are within two standard deviations from the centerline (the mean F_3). As for the F_3 values derived from the 12 monitoring samples and represented by the black markers on figure 5, two are beyond the LCL. Indeed, their corresponding fraud loss amount are above that tolerable by the business leaders, which further supports the consistency between the model's statistical and business performances as noted in sections 4.5.e and 4.5.1.

In general, under the normality assumption, control charts can be used to answer some important questions that model monitoring is concerned with, including but not limited to:

- how often can there be a false alarm?
- How quickly can small shift be detected?
- How quickly can a large shift be detected?
- How to detect unusual patterns even when the monitored statistic is within control limits.

The answers to these questions can greatly benefit the monitoring of quantitative models given the dynamic socio-economic environment that influence their input variables. More importantly, these answers can assist data scientists and business leaders better understand the variation in their model performance and thereby avoid wasting significant amount of time and resources in unnecessary roots cause analysis, model redevelopment or worse failing to stop the use of under-performing models.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we showed that the selection of the statistical performance metric is crucial to an effective model monitoring. In the presence of several statistical performance metrics, data scientists may be tempted to select the most popular metric or one that can favorably support the approval of their model. While that approach may be acceptable during the initial model review, it may lead to tremendous waste of time and resources and significant business costs during the model monitoring. We showed that selecting a statistical performance metric that concurs with the business leader's KPI is an important criterion to not only understand the model's contribution to the overall business objective but can also help determine whether the model is at fault when the business objective is not met. In addition to the selection of the appropriate statistical performance metric for monitoring purpose, we also showed that conducting a hypothesis testing rather than relying on a single monitoring threshold provides a more rigorous assessment of whether the model is performing within tolerable range set by the data scientists and the business leaders. Finally, we propose that, under certain distributional assumption, the monitoring of quantitative models can benefit from some unique features of control charts, which can be the subject of a future study.

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Appendix

Appendix 1: Model selection

The random forest rf_max6 was selected over the other two candidates due to higher precision, recall or F1:

DTC_ent5 = DecisionTreeClassifier (criterion= 'entropy', max_depth=5, random_state=42)

LR = LogisticRegression (random_state=42)

Scorer/Metric	0	1	Accuracy	Macro avg	Weighted avg	Classifier
precision	0.98	0.14	0.86	0.56	0.96	DTC_ent5
Recall	0.86	0.63	0.86	0.75	0.86	DTC_ent5
F1_score	0.92	0.23	0.86	0.58	0.90	DTC_ent5
precision	0.98	0.13	0.88	0.56	0.95	Lr_lbfgs
Recall	0.90	0.43	0.88	0.66	0.88	Lr_lbfgs
F1_score	0.94	0.20	0.88	0.57	0.91	Lr_lbfgs
precision	0.99	0.17	0.88	0.58	0.96	Rf_max6
Recall	0.89	0.63	0.88	0.76	0.88	Rf_max6
F1_score	0.94	0.27	0.88	0.60	0.91	Rf_max6

Appendix 2:

Although the Recall metric yields a stronger linear relationship compared to F1_score, this relationship was not as strong as that of the F3 which has $R^2 = 94\%$.

Appendix 3: F3 and Fraud loss for the 12 monitoring samples

F3	Fraud Loss
0.88601	72243
0.896539	66228
0.896459	65259
0.881892	77847
0.899977	64497
0.889805	72135
0.883944	77421
0.839315	109578
0.874106	81855
0.810488	129270
0.880704	76812
0.876385	80229